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PROTECT THE SLOPES OF THE LAND POLO.

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Abstract: This article discusses the methods and types of protection of railway land polotno slopes from the erosion process, where precipitation and wind are the main causes of erosion. Railways land polotno slopes are built and put into operation in the dimensions specified in the regulatory documents during the construction process. After a certain period of time, wind and water begin to affect the slopes of the Earth's polotno, due to the construction area as well as the grunt properties on which the canopy is erected, and this can negatively affect the safe transfer of trains at a specified speed of the Earth's polotno structure. In the event that the local stability of the slopes of the land polotno is not ensured, measures are prescribed to strengthen the slopes. Below were considered the types of slope landscaping and adopted the type suitable for strengthening the slopes of the land polotnosi, built from sand grunt on the Bukhara-Misken railway.

Key words: Land polotno, land polotno slope, water and wind erosion, protection from the erosion process, methods of strengthening the land polotno, geosynthetic materials.

INTRODUCTION

Increasing the attractiveness of intercity and suburban railway traffic, increasing the number of foreign tourists to 15 million, the number of domestic tourists to 25 million, the number of tourists coming for pilgrimage tourism to 3 million, the volume of transit cargo through the territory of the Republic to 16 million tons, the share of electrified railways to 65% delivery, prevention of climate change and soil erosion, prevention of dust storms is one of the priority goals of the development strategy of Uzbekistan until 2030 [1,2].

Currently, ensuring lift reliability in the protection and strengthening of land polotnosi slopes from the erosion process based on the application of various innovative technologies and materials in developed

countries is becoming important in the stages of design, construction and operation of Railways [2,3].

The Railway Ground track is the most responsible element of the railway track, the load-bearing structure [2,4].

There are a large number of deformations in the terrain of existing roads. And in order to fulfill the task of increasing the speed of movement, it is necessary to strengthen with modern technologies and materials at present [2,5].

On railways, the slopes of the land polotno are affected by wind and precipitation water, depending on the type of grunt, which creates an erosion process.

Erosion is the process of gradual erosion of mountain rocks and grunts under the influence of watercourses and wind. The

erosion process is divided by degree into natural and anthropogenic types [2,6].

Also known as wind erosion deflation. Wind erosion is the destructive effect of wind. Wind erosion occurs mainly in desert areas, in large open areas that are not protected by vegetation, it means that the particles of the fertile layer are blown away by the wind itself. Wind erosion is capable of occupying large gaps, especially very dangerous for dry land massifs.

The climatic feature is long-term rainfall or melting of large amounts of snow these are characteristic of water erosion. Melt waters will suck up the soil and cause damage. Wind erosion is typical of flat zones with dry climates, because in areas with low rainfall, the soil dries up quickly [6,7,8].

Grunt features-play an important role in the erosion process. Black soils are the most stable, such grunts do not disappear in practice in the wind and water. Soil and Sandy grunts, on the other hand, are characterized by the least stagnation [8].

Today, looking at the location status of the Railways of Uzbekistan, they are being exploited in different climatic conditions.

Today, weak grunts serve as the basis in the construction sector in Uzbekistan, namely in the construction of hydraulic structures, railways and highways, which is considered one of the complex problems that need to be solved [9,10,11].

METHOD OF RESEARCH

The types of reinforcement and protection of the Earth's plotno from the erosion process depend on the size and importance of the structure, topography, climate, groundwater and hydrogeological conditions, locally available materials, construction deadlines and other factors. The type of structural reinforcement is

distinguished depending on the material and technology used for reinforcement [12,13,14].

Biotechnical reinforcement methods

- Planting deep-rooted plants: planting plants with a deep and branched growing root system to strengthen the deep layers of the grunt.

- Use of lawns and covering plants: creating a dense vegetation cover to protect the slope surface from erosion.

- Fences and biological beds: a combination of living plants with biodegradable beds and nets to create fences from living plants or protect against erosion and strengthen slopes.

- Hydrosepma: spraying a mixture of seeds, fertilizers and binders on slopes to quickly create a plant cover [12,13,14].

Method of reinforcement with geosynthetic materials

- Geotextile is a conductive fabric used for separation, filtration, reinforcement, protection and drainage. Geotextiles prevent mixing of different grunt layers and promote efficient water drainage by lowering pressure and preventing erosion.

- Geopanjaras-used to strengthen the grunt by creating a reinforced layer. Geopanjaras effectively distribute the load, increasing the stability and load capacity of the grunt.

- Geomembranes are waterproof polymer films that are waterproof and used to protect against water penetration. They prevent erosion and control fluid migration.

- Geomates are three-dimensional materials with an open structure that are used to protect the upper layers of the grunt from erosion. Geomates help to hold the grunt and stimulate plant growth.

- Geocomposites combine the properties of two or more geosynthetic materials, such

as geotextile and geopanlara, providing a comprehensive solution for reinforcement, drainage and filtration [13,14].

Concrete structures

• Protective walls are usually used to hold the grout and prevent it from sliding or falling. They can be made of monolithic concrete or assembled from concrete blocks.

• Concrete blocks and slabs are used to create a protective layer on the surface of the slope. They can be laid with a certain step to drain and ventilate the grout.

• Concrete elements such as gabions (concrete boxes filled with stones) or special erosion-resistant blocks are designed to protect slopes from erosion and help strengthen the grout [13,14].

Stone structures

Stone structures include stone work, gabions, and stone cladding of various slopes. These methods combine the natural beauty of the stone with the high efficiency of erosion protection.

• Stone work can be used to create protective walls or cover slopes. Stones are laid by hand or using a special technique, ensuring the strength and stability of the structure.

• Gabions are mesh wire vessels filled with stones. They are widely used to strengthen the banks, slopes and slopes of rivers due to their flexibility, strength and water permeability, which prevents erosion of the grout.

• Covering the slopes with stone not only protects the surface from erosion, but also gives the landscape a natural and aesthetically attractive appearance [13,14].

Strengthening the slopes with piles

Piles are long elements that can be made of various materials (metal, concrete, wood) and buried in the ground to increase its load-

bearing capacity and stabilize the slopes. Piles transfer the load from the surface layers of the grout to denser and more stable layers of greater depth.

• High load capacity and load resistance.

• Possibility of use in different geological conditions.

• Durability and reliability of the reinforced slope [13,14].

Strengthening the slopes with an anchor

• Anchors (grout anchors) are elements used to create a pre — voltage to the ground, which allows it to increase displacement and collapse resistance. The anchors are mounted in pre-drilled wells (skewers) and secured to the ground, after which they are pulled and thus create a holding force [13,14].

RESEARCH RESULTS

We will have to take into account the following if we analyze the strengthening of Railway Ground Polo slopes in sandy conditions, depending on the above methods and materials and the technology of their application.

Strengthening the slopes with the help of piles and anchors is possible to accurately control the tension of piles and anchors, as well as a good solution for strengthening in difficult conditions, but not considered an economical solution for sandy conditions.

The use of concrete and Stone also protects the Earth's plotno slope from the erosion process, increasing the priority of the slope, and its application, despite being resistant to weathering, is also not considered an economical solution on large-scale surfaces in sandy conditions.

As for geosynthetic materials, they have a high strength, are resistant to the environment, have a low consumption of mehnat and mehanism and provide favorable conditions for the growth of plants,

considering that biotechnical method i.e. when applied together with the sowing of seeds of local plants, high indicators can be achieved and at favorable prices.

CONCLUSIONS

In the general structure, it is necessary to ensure the stability of the slope of the ground floor, increasing reliability and durability in use on all categories of roads. At the same time, strengthening, prioritizing and evaluating the slope of the land Polo requires an integrated approach. Measures to ensure the reliability of railway infrastructure facilities are carried out at the time of new construction or during the period of overhaul. One of the priority issues is the development and introduction of methods for strengthening the slope of the railway land Polo. In complex engineering and geological conditions, the use of geosynthetic materials in land polotnose structures built from Barkhan Sands is more important in terms of reliability than in one-time cost savings in increasing the performance capacity and transport-operation reliability of the structure. World experience in the use of geosynthetic materials indicates their versatility (wide scope), efficiency (reducing construction and operation costs, saving building materials, reducing working hours), environmental friendliness (reducing the use of Natural Resources) [15,16,17].

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